

INSILICO
WORLD

**LOWERING
BARRIERS**
TO IN SILICO TRIALS

VPH2024

IN SILICO WORLD FINAL MEETING

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Message from our coordinator

Prof. Marco Viceconti
University of Bologna

When the first three years of work were evaluated by the European Commission experts, the **In Silico World** project was already reported as a total success. As less than four months separate us from the end of the project, this is becoming more and more evident.

The landscape around in silico trials at the end of 2024 is hugely different from what we described in the proposal we wrote in 2019, and this project has **played a considerable role** in this transformation.

With **11 solutions** released, **6 validation collections** in open access, the publication of the **GSP book**, the key role we played in the new IEC-ISO workgroup on **credibility**, the report on the two complex **qualification advice with EMA**, a massive collection of resources to better **inform all stakeholders**, precious resources for **training and retraining**, and a systematic analysis of the **ethical and legal landscape**, In Silico World has been transformational at many levels.

Saying that I am proud to coordinate this merry band of brothers would not explain how happy I am to close my research career on such a high note. **Well done!!**

The project

As the In Silico World project nears its conclusion, the achievements and advancements made since its beginning in January 2021 are evident. **Coordinated by the Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna** and funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, the project brought together **14 partner institutions** in a collaborative effort to push the boundaries of in silico trials.

Over the course of the project, significant progress has been made in the development of **11 solutions aimed at testing the safety and efficacy of medical devices, medicinal products,** and advanced therapy medicinal products. These solutions target a range of conditions, including osteoporosis, tuberculosis, multiple sclerosis, coronary stenosis, cerebral aneurysms, mammary carcinoma, and COVID-19, among others.

As the project approaches its final stages, the consortium has successfully produced key deliverables, including **data collections for validation, regulatory pathways, and technical standards.** Additionally, comprehensive policy documents and information packages have been created for various

stakeholders, including patients, doctors, and senior management in companies. The project has also developed computational strategies to **enhance the power and efficiency of simulations,** new educational curricula to prepare the workforce for the adoption of in silico trial technologies, and robust business models to **support the commercial exploitation** of these technologies. All efforts have been carried out with careful consideration of the legal and ethical implications associated with these disruptive technologies.

The enthusiasm and collaborative spirit have been sustained throughout the project, with communication playing a crucial role in accelerating the adoption of in silico trials. By building trust in these innovative technologies, influencing the design of regulatory trials, and solidifying regulatory pathways, the project has laid the groundwork for the continued growth and acceptance of in silico trials in the medical field.

The consortium

The In Silico World consortium sees the participation of **world-class leading scientists, technological researchers, clinicians, and companies on in silico medicine** from six European countries working together with a large multi-stakeholder advisory board to provide several resources that will permanently lower barriers to a wider adoption of in silico trials.

We count on a total of **more than 100 professionals from 17 partner institutions** including universities, companies, research hospitals, an international research centre, a non-governmental organisation and a standardisation body.

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna (UNIBO)

UNIBO is the project Coordinator. Most of the activities assigned to partner UNIBO in the ISW project are responsibility of the In Silico Medicine Group led by Prof Marco Viceconti, based at the Department of Industrial Engineering.

Universiteit van Amsterdam (UvA)

The Computational Science Lab of the faculty of Science of the University of Amsterdam aims to describe and understand how complex systems in nature and society process information. UvA participates in the project providing its competences in advanced modelling, regulatory aspects, and computing aspects.

UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM

Virtual Physiological Human Institute for Integrative Biomedical Research vzw (VPHi)

The VPHi is an international non-profit organization whose mission is to ensure that the Virtual Physiological Human (VPH), also identified with the terminology "in silico medicine", is fully realised, universally adopted, and effectively used both in research and clinics.

Technische Universiteit Eindhoven (TU/e)

Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e) is a research university specialising in engineering science & technology. TU/e leads and is mainly involved in the curation of different validation data collections, in legal provisions and relevant ethical considerations, for the aspects of data management.

Università degli Studi di Catania (UNICT)

In the Department of Drug and Health Sciences, the Computational Systems Biomedicine Research Group – COMBINE drives the research in applying computational methodologies to the field of biomedicine.

Università
di Catania

Sano Centrum Zindywidualizowanej Medycyny

Sano – Centre for Computational Personalised Medicine – International Research Foundation is taking a leading role in building Europe's foremost centre for the advancement of computational medicine. Sano is responsible for providing the scalable and efficient computing platform.

Katholieke Universiteit Leuven (KU Leuven)

KU Leuven contributes with four entities: KU Leuven-MEC representing the Biomechanics Section in the Faculty of Engineering Science, KUL-CTP representing the KU Leuven Centre for IT and IP Law, KU Leuven-HMB representing the Human Movement Biomechanics group, and KU Leuven-LSS representing the Life Sciences and Society lab.

KU LEUVEN

InSilicoTrials Technologies Srl (IST)

IST was founded in 2012 (with the original name of Promeditec) to offer innovative solutions and specialised consultancy for clinical trials, e.g. web-based integrated platforms for the management of clinical data, images and documents.

Din Deutsches Institut fuer Normung E.V. (DIN)

DIN is a non-profit organization recognised as a German National Standards Body that supports any R&D projects with the concept of R&D Phase Standardisation, from early identification of standardisation potential of products and services, establishment of standardisation processes, and assistance with public availability of the results of these processes.

Université de Liege (ULIEGE)

The Biomechanics Research Unit at the University of Liege focuses on the development of in silico and in vitro tools for skeletal tissue engineering and lymphangiogenesis applications. ULIEGE contributes providing an application in the ATMP therapy domain.

Budapesti Muszaki Es Gazdasagtudomanyi Egyetem (BME)

The Department of Hydrodynamic Systems at Budapest University of Technology and Economics specialises on various aspects of applied fluid mechanics. One key research field is hemodynamics. The group has extensive experience in in silico aneurysm research.

M Ű E G Y E T E M 1 7 8 2

Mimesis Srl (MIM)

MIMESIS SRL is an innovative start-up founded in 2020 and it represents a pioneering SME whose aim is to provide to the biomedical industry the first generation of in silico trials solutions for the evaluation of safety and efficacy of medicinal products.

Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam (EMC)

At Erasmus Medical Center, the Biomechanics group focuses on the biomechanics of the development of atherosclerotic plaques in the human carotid and coronary arteries in close collaboration with the Interventional Cardiology, Radiology and Epidemiology departments.

Materialise Motion NV

Materialise Motion NV is a technology company that develops biomechanical measuring equipment and analysis software for the objective evaluation of human movement.

Barriers to in silico trials

LACK OF ADVANCED MODELS

Predictive models are in many cases not advanced and robust enough to be used in the reduction, refinement and/or replacement of the clinical trials required for the certification of new medical products.

OUR GOAL: Develop more advanced models for the evaluation of safety and efficacy for both medicinal and medical device products that address specific Contexts of Use but at the same time enable a completely new class of models of disease with a similar pathogenesis.

POORLY INFORMED STAKEHOLDERS

It is crucial to give clear and correct information to all stakeholders (policymakers, patients, doctors, regulators, healthcare payers, Contract Research Organisations, technology providers, executives of biomedical companies, etc.) on the opportunities and the risks associated with the use of in silico trials technologies. Each stakeholder will thus benefit of a rigorous risk-benefit evaluation framework to assess the adoption of in silico trials technologies.

OUR GOAL: Policies-watch; risk-benefit and cost-benefit analyses for healthcare professionals; monitor perception of IST among senior management of medical industries; promote citizen trust in IST.

LACK OF INDEPENDENT VALIDATION COLLECTIONS

We need widely available collections of curated medical data specifically designed for the development and the validation of in silico trials technologies.

OUR GOAL: Define requirements for data used as inputs of in silico trials models; analyse contexts of use and define requirements for validation collections; organise collections of existing data; support the formation of prospective collections.

LACK OF TRAINED WORKFORCE

It is rare to find professionals that have the necessary technical skills on in silico trials to work in industry, regulatory agencies, research hospitals, etc., because of the lack of opportunities for training and re-training.

OUR GOAL: Re-training of technical and non-technical professionals on the use, opportunities, and the potential threats IST can provide; revision of the curricula of both technical and non-technical biomedical education to include IST elements.

POOR SCALABILITY AND EFFICIENCY

At the moment, most in silico trials models have insufficient scalability, as long as the lack of efficient computing of large-scale population models in easy-to-use, safe, and trusted environments.

OUR GOAL: Improve efficiency (cost and duration) of IST simulations; improve scalability of existing IST solutions, to handle large-scale simulations (from sensitivity analysis to populations); from big data to big simulations: user interfaces to supervise thousands of simulation results; implications of the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR) for large-scale IST simulations.

LACK OF BUSINESS MODELS

There is not a clear business model that regulates how to sell in silico applications and services. Different companies use different business models and this leads to an unclear commercial exploitation trajectory.

OUR GOAL: The In Silico World consortium plans to analyse and define the market sectors involved in the potential business opportunities for the solutions and collections developed in the framework of the project. Once higher visibility in the European community will be achieved through cluster activities, business models and strategies will be developed – in terms of value creation and market orientation – to successfully put on the market system.

NO CLEAR REGULATORY PATHWAYS

The credibility assessment proposed in the ASME VV-40 technical standard is limited to models used to assess medical devices. Pharmaceutical products, Advanced Therapy Medicinal Products, and Combinatory products do not have yet an equivalent standard. Also, the VV-40 is not harmonised in the CEN standardisation framework, which makes it unclear on whether it can be used in relation to CE marking submissions. "First in kind" qualifications of in silico trials methods for the evaluation of drugs with EMA are proceeding quite slowly. Also, we need to explore new regulatory pathways for class III medical devices and pharmaceutical products that allow a significant reduction of human experimentation with in silico trials technologies, and the adoption of a rigorous post-marketing surveillance that monitors the validity of the in silico predictions as the new product is adopted.

OUR GOAL: Develop good regulatory practices for the qualification of in silico trial models to assess medical devices and medicinal products; pursue first-in-kind qualification of existing solutions.

Multi-stakeholder Advisory Board

In these years, the collaboration with the Multi-stakeholder Advisory Board (MAB) has proven to be a **pivotal element in fostering a Community of Practice** around in silico trials. This community brings together **academics, industry experts, regulators, clinicians, and patients** to build consensus on Good Modeling Practices. Throughout the project, the role of the Advisory Board has been especially significant. Recognising that the successful adoption of in silico trials requires **broad collaboration**, the InSilicoWorld consortium has actively engaged with representatives from **all key stakeholder groups**, including researchers, industry professionals, payers, citizens, medical professionals, regulators, and policymakers.

While the **MAB's primary focus** has been on regulatory aspects and the communication of the risks and benefits associated with in silico trials, its influence has extended much further. The MAB has been regularly informed and consulted on the project's main activities, ensuring that the perspectives of all stakeholder groups are considered. As the project nears its end, the MAB continues to serve as a consulting and advisory body, shaping the implementation of specific project components and providing a comprehensive evaluation of the project's outcomes. This collaborative approach has been **instrumental in overcoming barriers** to the adoption of in silico trials and ensuring the project's success.

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(a few)

Project Results

The ISW Community of Practice represented in the IEC & ISO Committees

Thanks to the **leading role** and the **amazing collegial effort** of a long list of people working on the **In Silico World project**, the Avicenna Alliance is joining the **IEC TC 62 & ISO/TC 276/WG5 Committees** and will represent our Community of Practice in this process.

This was a long journey and now we are about to set an important milestone on the concrete possibility of developing an **IEC-ISO** equivalent to the ASME VV-40, which could be **harmonised in the CE marking system**.

Reflecting on the steps that led us here, the vision and dedication exhibited by all involved parties have been paramount. This initiative is a remarkable example of this collaborative spirit. The establishment of the IEC/ISO workgroup and the pivotal role played by the **VPH Institute** and **Avicenna Alliance** in overcoming the transitory nature of our projects demonstrate the agility and commitment of our community to achieving meaningful outcomes. A long list of people and organisations contributed to these excellent results, and we thank all of them.

Thanks to Prof. Marco Viceconti from Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna, Prof. Liesbet Geris from VPHi and coordinator of the EDITH-CSA project, Prof. Francesco Pappalardo from Università di Catania, our DIN Deutsches Institut für Normung e. V. colleagues Klaus Zeier and Heike Moser, and experts like Jeff Bischoff and Marc Horner, Ph.D., who sit in the ASME-VV40 committee.

**Join the ISW
Community
of Practice!**

The In Silico World Solutions

The project advanced the development of **11 in silico trial solutions**, designed to test the safety and/or the efficacy of medical devices, medicinal products, and even advanced therapy medicinal products such as tissue engineering constructs for regenerative medicine. The solutions target medical products to treat osteoporosis, tuberculosis, multiple sclerosis, coronary stenosis, cerebral aneurysms, mammary carcinoma, and covid-19 infection, among others.

- **AngioSupport**

Angiosupport is a 1D/0D model to predict pressure and flow waves in the coronary arteries based on standard bi-plane angiographic data although also CT-data can be used.

- **BoneStrength**

BoneStrength is an in silico trial solution to assess the efficacy of pharmacological treatments for osteoporosis and prevention of fragility fractures.

- **ForceLoss**

The ForceLoss project aims to enable the identification of the originating cause (differential diagnosis) of dynapenia, leveraging on the use of computer models of the human musculoskeletal system to support clinical decision making.

- **InSole**

InSole aims to combine subject-specific musculoskeletal models with novel predictive simulations for the personalised prescription of 3D printed corrective shoe insoles.

- **NeoIntima3D**

ISR3D is a specific example of a model for neointima (new tissue) formation in the cardiovascular system, which plays an especially large role in recovery after medical intravascular intervention, e.g. in healing and scar formation. NeoIntima3D uses a more general model to provide a solution that predicts the risk of late thrombosis in vascular stenting.

- **OCDefects**

OcDefects is a mechanobiology model of the osteochondral cartilage regeneration process, to be used for In Silico trials of an Advanced Therapeutic Medicinal Product (ATMP) for the repair of deep osteochondral defects.

- **UISS-COVID19**

UISS-COVID19 consists in an in silico platform that predicts the dynamics of SARS-CoV-2 immune system competition within the host.

- **UISS-MC**

The Universal Immune System Simulator – Mammary Carcinoma (UISS-MC) is an agent-based model specifically tailored to simulate the effects of tumor-preventive cell vaccines in HER-2/neutransgenic mice prone to the development of mammary carcinoma.

- **UISS-MS**

The Universal Immune System Simulator – Multiple Sclerosis (UISS-MS) predicts the outcome of specific treatments in patients affected by a relapsing-remitting form of multiple sclerosis.

- **UISS-TB**

The Universal Immune System Simulator – Tuberculosis (UISS-TB) is a simulator of the immune system dynamics, particularly tailored to predict the response of the human immune system to the exposure to *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

- **VirtualFD**

VirtualFD is a solution with a framework to simulate the virtual flow diverter (FD) deployment and the flow in and around intracranial aneurysms. The application takes into account the detailed mechanical properties and the hydrodynamic resistance of the FDs, both obtained from unique in-house measurements.

The Dutch team meeting up in Eindhoven

UNIBO team working on BoneStrength

The In Silico World Validation Data Collections

The In Silico World project is dedicated to advancing the development and validation of in silico trials technologies by making **widely available collections of curated medical data**. These datasets are meticulously curated to serve as vital resources for validating in silico trial solutions, offering researchers and clinicians around the globe **access to high-quality data** that can drive innovation and improve patient outcomes.

DATA COLLECTION	DISEASE	DATA TYPE	PARTNER
MSVALID	MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS	84 MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGES	UNIVERSITY OF CATANIA
TBVALID	PULMONARY TUBERCULOSIS	870 DIGITAL PATIENTS	UNIVERSITY OF CATANIA
STENTVALID	CARDIOVASCULAR	846 AND 1500 ANGIO-BASED CORONARY ARTERY DATASETS	ERASMUS MC
HFVALID	HIP-FRACTURE	101 CALIBRATED CT SCANS OF FEMURS	UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA
DPVALID	DYNAPENIA (LOSS OF MUSCLE FORCE)	20 3D RECONSTRUCTIONS OF MAJOR MUSCLES	UNIVERSITY OF BOLOGNA
VALVE VALID	CARDIOVASCULAR	MEASUREMENT SIZES OF THE AORTIC VALVE FROM 402 PATIENTS	EINDHOVEN UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

HFValid Collection: Hip-Fracture Validation Collection

The HFValid collection, produced by the University of Bologna and IRCCS Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli, is the first dataset released within the In Silico World project. It comprises 101 anonymised calibrated computed tomography (CT) scans of whole femurs, complete with segmentations and selected anatomical landmarks. This dataset provides a crucial resource for validating models related to hip fractures, enabling more accurate simulations and analyses in the field.

MSValid Collection: Multiple Sclerosis Validation Collection

Contributed by Università degli Studi di Catania (UNICT), the MSValid collection is an invaluable dataset for those researching multiple sclerosis (MS). Containing 84 anonymised magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans of MS patients, the data is presented in the NIfTI format, promoting easier sharing and analysis. This dataset is a significant milestone in democratising access to clinical data, offering a powerful tool for developing predictive models, understanding treatment variability, and uncovering new biomarkers for MS.

TBValid Collection: Tuberculosis Validation Collection

The TBValid collection, leverages data from dose versus immunogenicity response in tuberculosis patients and healthy volunteers to create a virtual cohort of 870 digital 'patients.' These profiles, generated from anonymised clinical trial data, offer a diverse representation of the population, aiding in the exploration of tuberculosis treatment responses. This innovative approach not only protects patient privacy but also enriches the potential for in silico trials.

StentValid Collection: Vascular Stent Validation Collection

Developed by Erasmus MC, the StentValid collection focuses on validating restenosis models for vascular stents. The dataset includes intravascular imaging data from 100 coronary artery disease patients treated with bioresorbable stents. With 200 data sets captured immediately after the procedure and at a 6-month follow-up, the collection includes detailed lumen, wall, and stent contour data. This information is vital for evaluating stent efficacy and understanding neointima formation, providing key insights for cardiovascular treatment research.

DPValid Collection: Dynapenia (loss of muscle force) Validation Collection

The DPValid dataset is composed of anonymised raw and processed data including surface electromyography and dynamometry data collected on 20 healthy adults (10 females, 10 males) during a maximum voluntary isometric contraction test. UNIBO used data collected at its linked third party Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli.

ValveValid: Aortic valve measurements Validation Collection

The ValveValid dataset offers detailed geometric measurements of the aortic valve from 402 patients, categorized by valve type. This dataset supports cardiac health research and includes measurements in millimeters for analysing aortic valve geometry. The document also provides guidelines for data usage.

All resources are available on

zenodo

Report on the “Regulatory barriers to the adoption of in silico trials”

Despite their enormous potential, the **adoption of in silico methodologies** in the regulatory evaluation of biomedical products (sometimes referred to as in silico trials) is growing slowly. During the initial analysis phase, the In Silico World consortium identified seven **barriers**; one was related to **regulatory aspects**.

During the four years of activity, the ISW consortium conducted **two qualification advice procedures** with the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and engaged with notified bodies, national authorities, and standardisation bodies.

In this report, we provided **detailed documentation** of all these activities so that any other interested party can learn from our experience.

Members of the ISW consortium were also instrumental in developing an open-access book published by Nature-Springer, entitled “**Toward Good Simulation Practice: best practices for the use of computational modelling & simulation in the regulatory process of biomedical products**”.

This book results from a long grass-root consensus process involving hundreds of international experts from academia, industry, clinical practice, and regulatory agencies. As we led this important debate and captured it in this book, several concepts that influenced the present report emerged.

Some of our experts were involved in the Mobilise-D project, which aimed to establish regulatory pathways for wearable mobility monitors in drug trials. We closely monitored the qualification advice procedures with the EMA, the FDA's CDER, and a Q-Sub request to the FDA's CDRH. While the Mobilise-D consortium is responsible for sharing related documentation, we will summarise some publicly available resources.

But this document's ambition is more than a merge report of these activities. In the following pages, we will reflect on how **biomedical regulatory science** can cope with the technological revolution pervading the **medical field**. We will report in detail the various exploratory activities we conducted as part of the In Silico World project, and from the **lessons learnt** from those, we will propose an analysis of the reasons for some resistance, which we believe goes back to the differences in pragmatic epistemologies of the expert scientists involved in the regulatory panels. Lastly, based on this analysis, we will draw some conclusions and make recommendations for policymakers and the in silico trials community.

The partners of the In Silico World consortium wrote this report, to learn more check the QR code.

The “Toward Good Simulation Practice” book

The In Silico World consortium is proud to announce that the “Toward Good Simulation Practice” book has been published and is now freely available to the whole in silico medicine community.

Such a great achievement is the result of a large collaboration of in silico experts around the world, coordinated by the In Silico World consortium (Prof. Marco Viceconti from Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna, Luca Emili CEO of InSilicoTrials) with the support of our VPH Institute partner, and Avicenna Alliance and FDA colleagues.

We brought together 138 experts in in silico trials working in academia, the medical industry, regulatory bodies, hospitals, and consulting firms. Through a consensus process, these experts produced the first attempt to define some Good Simulation Practices (GSP) on how to develop, evaluate, and use in silico trials. This constitutes an indispensable guide for anyone who is planning to engage at any title with in silico trials.

A long list of people and organisations contributed to these excellent results, and we thank all of them.

Access the full resource and learn more about the best practices for the use of computational modelling and simulation in the regulatory process of biomedical products.

**Access the
Good Simulation
Practice Book!**

12 Golden Rules on the Ethical and Legal aspects of in silico trials

In silico trials consist of the virtual testing of medical devices and medicinal products. They may help support the **regulatory approval process of a medical product** and, in general, the whole lifecycle of the medical product.

- **privacy**
- **data protection & data governance**
- **medical devices & medical products**
- **artificial intelligence**
- **ethics**

The document "Implementation guidance and guidelines", produced by partner KU Leuven and part of the "Ethical and Legal Framework" of the In Silico World project, offers guidelines on the ethical and legal aspects of in silico trials for researchers and end users.

Short and descriptive recommendations are provided for each of them. Check the QR code below to access the full resource.

The report builds on the previous reports "**Legal and Ethical Inventory**" and "**In-depth Analysis of Legal and Ethical Requirements**", which assessed the core pieces of legislation and ethical principles relevant to in silico trials.

It contains twelve **main recommendations** concerning the areas of legislation already identified in previous works:

Stakeholder engagement & education materials

It is crucial to give **clear and correct information to all stakeholders** (policymakers, patients, doctors, regulators, healthcare payers, Contract Research Organisations, technology providers, executives of biomedical companies, etc.) **on the opportunities and the risks associated with the use of in silico trials technologies**. It is also important to engage with all these stakeholders and involve them through a framework like responsible research and innovation (RRI). The fundamental approach followed in the ISW project to engage diverse stakeholder groups encompassed a series of steps (executed for the different stakeholder groups with some adaptations), thus, **understanding their needs**, capturing their **perceptions** and collecting their **concerns** on silico medicine.

To support the modelling and simulation community in engaging with key stakeholders, the Virtual Physiological Human Institute (VPHi) designed the **In Silico Medicine Info Kit**. It offers guidelines on effective interaction, information materials, multimedia examples, **handbook** to organise focus groups and surveys. Initial focus is about modellers. This evolving document will be regularly updated following the latest **advancement in the field**.

To address the lack of trained workforce on in silico technologies, partner KU Leuven has identified the **learning needs** of several stakeholder categories, such as engineering and medical students, or professionals active in relevant fields either with a medical, engineering or even legal background. **Learning material** is now being **developed** with a focus on offering it in an online self-learning platform. Lecture materials are being evaluated first in small groups of stakeholders, and then further refined.

ISW PEOPLE: 2024 General Assembly in Catania (Italy)

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